

Supplemental Material

S.1. STEPS INVOLVED IN THE HHL ALGORITHM (INCLUDING FEATURE EXTRACTION)

The HHL algorithm [1] broadly encompasses the following steps. Detailed reviews describing the HHL algorithm in general can be found in Refs. [2–4]:

- We initialize three qubit registers to the state $|b\rangle_s |0\rangle_c^{\otimes n_r} |0\rangle_a$. The subscript, ‘s’, denotes the state register, and it is assumed that the n_b -qubit state, $|b\rangle_s$, can be efficiently prepared from $|0\rangle_s$. $|b\rangle_s$ is obtained from normalized \vec{b} via amplitude encoding. Furthermore, $|b\rangle_s$ can be expanded in the eigenbasis of A as $|b\rangle_s = \sum_i b_i |v_i\rangle$. The subscripts ‘c’ and ‘a’ refer to the clock register (which contains n_r qubits) and the HHL ancillary qubit register respectively.
- Perform QPE on the clock and the state registers, in order to obtain the eigenvalues $\tilde{\lambda}_i$ of A captured using n_r bits. The state after QPE is $\sum_i b_i |v_i\rangle_s |\tilde{\lambda}_i\rangle_c |0\rangle_a$.
- Carry out a controlled-rotation module between the clock and the HHL ancilla registers, so that the eigenvalues are inverted. This can be done in more than one way, including the use of a suitably chosen uniformly controlled rotation circuit. The state after this step is $\sum_i b_i |v_i\rangle_s |\tilde{\lambda}_i\rangle_c \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{C^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_i^2}} |0\rangle_a + \frac{C}{\tilde{\lambda}_i} |1\rangle_a \right)$, where C is a suitably chosen constant.
- Undo QPE via a QPE^\dagger so that the HHL ancilla register is no longer entangled with the clock register. The state at the end of this step is $\sum_i b_i |v_i\rangle_s |0\rangle_c^{\otimes n_r} \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{C^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_i^2}} |0\rangle_a + \frac{C}{\tilde{\lambda}_i} |1\rangle_a \right)$.
- Measure the HHL ancilla qubit and post-select the outcome 1. We obtain $|x\rangle = \sum_i \frac{b_i}{\tilde{\lambda}_i} |v_i\rangle$ on the state register.
- Extract the feature of interest via an appropriate circuit. One could add an additional state register, $|b'\rangle$, initialized to a suitable state, so that this register along with the state register after HHL serve as inputs to a feature extraction circuit module. For example, this register could be initialized to $|b\rangle$, so

Figure S.1: Schematic of the HHL algorithm containing the HOM module to extract a feature from the solution vector.

that the output of a SWAP test [5] (or the Hong-Ou-Mandel (HOM) test, which is an ancilla-free version of the SWAP test but leads to destruction of state register qubits as a trade-off [6]) module yields an overlap between the solution vector and \vec{b}' .

A circuit that carries out the steps mentioned above (and for the specific example of extracting overlap between the input and output vectors) is illustrated in Fig. S.1.

S.2. SOME RELEVANT GRAPH THEORY DEFINITIONS

Definition S.2. 1. The degree of a vertex, $d(v)$, in a undirected graph G is defined by the number of edges incident on the vertex v .

Definition S.2. 2. An edge weight, w_{ij} , is a real number, which we assume to be positive throughout the article, which is assigned to an edge (v_i, v_j) .

Definition S.2. 3. A simple graph is an undirected graph without any self loop, edge weights, and multiple edges between the vertices.

Definition S.2. 4. A random graph may be a directed graph or an undirected graph where existence of an edge is probabilistic.

Definition S.2. 5. A graph $H = (V(H), E(H))$ is said to be a subgraph of a graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ if $V(H) \subset V(G)$ and $E(H) \subset E(G)$.

Definition S.2. 6. The degree matrix of an undirected simple graph G with N vertices $v_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is a

matrix $D(G) = (d_{ij})_{N \times N}$ where

$$d_{ij} = \begin{cases} d(i) & \text{if } i = j; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}, \quad (\text{S.1})$$

Here, $d(i)$ is the degree of vertex v_i . For a weighted undirected graph, $d(i)$ is the sum of the edge-weights of the edges incident on the vertex v_i .

Definition S.2. 7. The adjacency matrix, $Q(G) = (q_{ij})_{N \times N}$, of an undirected simple graph G with N vertices $v_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is defined by

$$q_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (v_i, v_j) \in E; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}. \quad (\text{S.2})$$

In case of a weighted graph, if w_{ij} is the weight of an edge (v_i, v_j) , we define

$$q_{ij} = \begin{cases} w_{ij} & \text{if } (v_i, v_j) \in E; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{S.3})$$

S.3. EXAMPLES OF NLSP

A Determining effective resistance in complex networks

Example 1. Electrical networks can be modeled as graphs, where each resistor is replaced by an edge, with the weight of the edge $(v_i, v_j) \in E$ being $w_{ij} = 1/r_{ij}$, where r_{ij} is the resistance of the edge. Consider the graph, G , given in the top right panel of Figure 1 of the main manuscript, which corresponds to an electrical network. Let u_1, u_2, u_3 , and u_4 represent the voltages at vertices v_1, v_2, v_3 , and v_4 respectively. We represent the currents entering the network at vertices v_1, v_2, v_3 , and v_4 as I_1, I_2, I_3 , and I_4 respectively. We assume there is no leakage of currents in the network. Hence, the amount of current entering the vertex is equal to the amount of current exiting the vertex. We choose the direction of flow of current as $v_1 \rightarrow v_2, v_2 \rightarrow v_3, v_3 \rightarrow v_4$ and $v_4 \rightarrow v_1$. We remark here that the choice of directions are arbitrary, and it does not affect the final equations. From the conservation of currents at every vertex of the network, we have the following set of equations:

$$\text{At } v_1 : (w_{12} + w_{41})u_1 - w_{12}u_2 - w_{41}u_4 = I_1 \quad (\text{S.4})$$

$$\text{At } v_2 : (w_{12} + w_{23})u_2 - w_{23}u_3 - w_{12}u_1 = I_2 \quad (\text{S.5})$$

$$\text{At } v_3 : (w_{34} + w_{23})u_3 - w_{34}u_4 - w_{23}u_2 = I_3 \quad (\text{S.6})$$

$$\text{At } v_4 : (w_{41} + w_{34})u_4 - w_{41}u_1 - w_{34}u_3 = I_4. \quad (\text{S.7})$$

These equations can then be written in the form of a matrix as follows:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} w_{12} + w_{41} & -w_{12} & 0 & -w_{41} \\ -w_{12} & w_{12} + w_{23} & -w_{23} & 0 \\ 0 & -w_{23} & w_{23} + w_{34} & -w_{34} \\ -w_{41} & 0 & -w_{34} & w_{34} + w_{41} \end{bmatrix}}_L \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{u}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \\ I_3 \\ I_4 \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{I}}. \quad (\text{S.8})$$

The above matrix represents the Laplacian matrix L of graph G . Here, \vec{u} is the vector of potentials, with each element of the vector providing the potential at a corresponding vertex of the network. \vec{I} is the vector of currents entering each vertex of the network. In general, for any electrical network modeled as an undirected graph, we have

$$L\vec{u} = \vec{I}. \quad (\text{S.9})$$

Here, \vec{u} is the unknown vector \vec{x} and \vec{I} takes the place of \vec{b} in equation $L\vec{x} = \vec{b}$. This equation assists us to solve for the vector of potentials. We use $\vec{u} = L^+\vec{I}$ to compute the effective resistance between two vertices, say v_1 and v_2 of the graph, where L^+ is pseudo-inverse of L . This is obtained by allowing a unit current to flow into the network at v_1 and out of the network at v_2 . We define $\vec{\delta}_i = (0, 0, \dots, 1, \dots, 0)^T$, where 1 occurs only at i^{th} index. To find effective resistance between v_1 and v_2 , we set $I_1 = 1$ unit of current and $I_2 = -1$ unit of current in Eq. S.8. Thus, $\vec{I} = \vec{\delta}_1 - \vec{\delta}_2$. As we allow only a unit current to enter and exit from vertices v_1 and v_2 respectively, finding effective resistance is as simple as finding the potential difference between vertices v_1 and v_2 . Hence, $r_{\text{eff}}^{12} = u_1 - u_2 = (\vec{\delta}_1 - \vec{\delta}_2)^T L^+ (\vec{\delta}_1 - \vec{\delta}_2)$. \square

B Determining number of vehicles on a lane: traffic flow congestion detection

Example 2. Consider the directed graph \vec{G} depicted in the top right panel of Figure 1 of the main manuscript where all the vertices v_1, v_2, v_3 , and v_4 preserve the flow conservation property. Viewed as a traffic flow problem, the edges are the lanes, while the weights on the edges denote the number of vehicles on that lane. The vehicles along a lane move in a particular direction, and is given by the direction marked on an edge. The vertices are the junctions. The vertices v_1 and v_4 take c_1 and c_4 vehicles respectively into the system of lanes. On the other hand, c_2 and c_3 are the number of vehicles that go out of the system via v_2 and v_3 respectively. The values of c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 are known. Let the flows via $\overrightarrow{(v_1, v_2)}, \overrightarrow{(v_2, v_3)}, \overrightarrow{(v_3, v_4)}$ be $\overrightarrow{(v_4, v_1)}$ are y_1, y_2, y_3 , and y_4 , respectively, which are

unknowns. As the flow conservation property holds at all the vertices, we can construct four linear equations for the vertices, which are as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \text{At } v_1 : -y_1 + y_4 + c_1 = 0 &\Rightarrow y_4 - y_1 = -c_1, \\ \text{At } v_2 : -y_2 + y_1 - c_2 = 0 &\Rightarrow -y_2 + y_1 = c_2, \\ \text{At } v_3 : -y_3 + y_2 - c_3 = 0 &\Rightarrow -y_3 + y_2 = c_3, \\ \text{At } v_4 : -y_4 + y_3 + c_4 = 0 &\Rightarrow -y_4 + y_3 = -c_4. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S.10})$$

These set of linear equations can be written in terms of a matrix equation

$$\underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}}_B \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \end{pmatrix}}_{\vec{y}} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} -c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \\ -c_4 \end{pmatrix}}_{\vec{c}}. \quad (\text{S.11})$$

The system of linear equations can be expressed as $B\vec{y} = \vec{c}$, where B is the incidence matrix of the graph \vec{G} , \vec{y} is the vector of flows on each edge, which is unknown in the equation and \vec{c} is the vector of flows entering the network at each vertex, which is a known quantity. To solve for \vec{y} using a quantum algorithm, we must transform our matrix B according to Equation (6) of the main manuscript. Our new matrix equation becomes

$$\underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 & B \\ B^\dagger & 0 \end{pmatrix}}_H \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vec{y} \end{pmatrix}}_{\vec{Y}} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \vec{c} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}}_{\vec{C}}. \quad (\text{S.12})$$

We compute \vec{Y} by solving $\vec{Y} = H^+ \vec{C}$, where H^+ is the pseudo-inverse of H . To get the flow over any edge, say y_i , we evaluate the overlap between $\vec{\delta}_i \cdot \vec{y}$. We note that in the case of traffic flow congestion detection problem, this overlap yields the number of vehicles on a lane. \square

S.4. SCOPE AND ASSUMPTIONS OF OUR NUMERICAL ANALYSES

It is important to stress that taking an analytical route to obtain the information on spectra of these graph families is very non-trivial. Thus, we rather resort to numerical analysis, which is not only computationally taxing at large system sizes but also naturally comes with non-trivial assumptions. In this section, we provide the scope and assumptions made in our calculations, accompanied by error analysis on representative graph families whenever possible.

A Assumptions

Figure S.2: An illustration of cut-off problem with (a) ladder graph family, and (b) with ring of cliques graph family. Sub-figure (c) provides a comparison of $\tilde{R}(n)$ versus n for CLS and KMP algorithms. The y-axis is on the log scale.

- **$1/\epsilon$ scaling:** As noted earlier, we assume for simplicity that $\epsilon^{-1} \sim \log(\mathcal{N})$. This assumption is reasonable, since for example, in HHL, this translates to n_r growing as $\log(\log(\mathcal{N}))$, where n_r is the number of clock register qubits in the HHL quantum

circuit Section S.1). This assumption can be relaxed depending on the specific application and target precision of interest in future studies.

- We only consider graph Laplacians with **edge weight of each edge set to 1**, for simplicity. A more general version of the analysis can be performed by relaxing this constraint for a future study, but for the purposes of this work, we perform preliminary analysis to inspect the effect of this assumption in obtaining advantage. We note that changing the edge weight of 1 for all of the edges to any other fixed real scalar for all of the edges does not affect κ or s . Thus, we consider three cases of non-uniform edge weights, where they grow linearly, polynomially (second order), and logarithmically, in y , where an edge occurs between two vertices carrying indices x and y . We carry out the analysis on two of the good graphs (refer Table II of the main manuscript): (i) the hypercube graph, and (ii) modified Margulis-Gabber-Galil graph. Our results are presented in Figs. S.3 and S.4. We make the important observation that edge weight values do impact prospects of advantage; the hypercube graph retains its exponential advantage with HHL, CKS(1)/AQC(1) and dream QLS (refer Table I of main manuscript) for logarithmically growing edge weights, but becomes a bad graph (i.e., no advantage with HHL) when edge weights grow as a linear or a polynomial (second order) function of y . However, we do get exponential advantage with CKS(1)/AQC(1) for linearly or polynomially growing edge weights, while these scenarios show no advantage with dream QLS. For weighted modified Margulis-Gabber-Galil graph family, when the edge weight grows logarithmically as well as linearly, the graph family still remains in the good category and exhibits exponential advantage for HHL, CKS(1)/AQC(1) and the dream QLS. If the the edge weights grow polynomially (second order), the graph family is demoted to a bad graph family, which implies no advantage with HHL algorithm. We also find that, with polynomially growing edge weights, CKS(1)/AQC(1) and dream QLS show exponential advantage.
- **Cut-off problem:** To calculate the condition number, κ , of a matrix, one must be able to distinguish the minimum eigenvalue with zero. Since we carry out numerical analyses, one can immediately see that eigenvalues smaller than a certain value may not be capturable, thus leading to an incorrect estimate for κ . For instance, if we are not able to

capture the minimum eigenvalue but instead end up capturing a larger one, we underestimate κ , and thus overestimate the degree of advantage obtained from that graph family. For all of our numerical calculations, we found that a cut-off of 10^{-6} for minimum eigenvalue is sufficient for the \mathcal{N} values up to which we calculate κ . The pertinent data, where we compare the minimum eigenvalues at a few system sizes for two different thresholds, 10^{-6} and 10^{-10} , and find them to be the same, is presented in Figs. S.5 and S.6. We note that the figures are only plotted for those graphs whose minimum eigenvalues show a downward trend with \mathcal{N} . Furthermore, when we move to \mathcal{N} values larger than those considered for our study, we find two exceptions: the ladder graph family and the ring of cliques graph family. Figs. S.2(a) and (b) highlight this ‘cut-off’ problem for these two graph families.

- **The horizon problem:** Since for practical reasons, a numerical analysis can only go up to some finite value of \mathcal{N} , our assessment for advantage may be inaccurate, since there is always a possibility for the fit functional form to change as we reach much larger system sizes. Such a change would be hidden beyond the largest \mathcal{N} that we pick for our numerical studies. We found three graph families: grid 2d graph, hexagonal lattice graph and triangular lattice graph, which exhibited different functional forms for condition number with the increase in system size. We also add at this juncture that the horizon problem is not avoidable and is fundamental, since we are using a classical computer (to compute κ) to assess quantum advantage. That is, to find if a QLS offers an advantage for a graph family, we must restrict our N or N' values (up to which we compute κ subject to classical computing limitations) and then extrapolate our findings, subject now to the horizon problem, to larger system sizes in order to predict a potential onset of quantum advantage.
- **Choice of other graph input parameters:** We saw earlier the effect of edge weight choice on the prospect of realizing an advantage. Other graph input parameters such as choice of seed value may also influence our conclusions. For our analyses presented in the main text, we fix the seed value for reproducibility of our results. To understand the influence of seed values, we pick three representative candidates: Barabási-Albert graph family from Laplacian matrix based system of linear equations, Gaussian random partition graph (no source and sink) family, and planted

partition graph (no source and sink) family from incidence matrix based system of linear equations. The results of our analyses are presented in Fig. S.7. For each graph family, we pick three different seed values and analyze the advantage offered by the respective graph families. We find that for the candidates that we consider, there is no change in their category upon changing the seed values. For example, the Barabási-Albert graph, which is a good graph, remains a good graph. Although the categories do not change for the graph families for the seed values that we considered for them, our observations cannot be generalized, and this aspect requires further analysis in a future study. The effect of tuning other parameters on advantage is also beyond the scope of our current work, and we defer it for a future study.

B Scope of our numerical study

- **Number of quantum linear solvers considered:** Although we consider several efficient QLSs for our survey, we do exclude some, such as the quantum singular value transformation (QSVT)-based QLS. While QSVT is important due to its potential to offer near-optimal scaling in κ and ϵ , we do not consider it due to the non-trivial nature of \mathcal{N} dependence entering via block encoding costs in its complexity. Other near-optimally scaling approaches built using block encoding have been excluded for the same reason (for example, the discrete adiabatic method [7] and the Zeno eigenstate filtering method [8]). Furthermore, algorithms such as AQC(exp) and CKS approaches that we consider in our study also scale near-optimally in κ and s , and thus they may provide a reasonable idea of what to expect in this context from the approaches that we have excluded. Lastly, our analysis includes a ‘dream QLS’ whose scaling is more favourable than any of the quantum linear solvers that we do not consider for our survey.
- **Number of graph families considered:** Since we carry out a numerical study, we are limited in the choice of graph families that we consider. Thus, our conclusions on the percentage of graph families that are best or better also are reliant heavily on the choice of graph families for our survey. Future work needs to be done in surveying broader classes of graphs for QLSs, especially given the dearth of literature on this front.
- In our numerical analyses, we substitute κ and s obtained from our numerical dataset (which usually do not exceed \mathcal{N} of 10000) into runtime ratios, even though the runtime expressions themselves are for large \mathcal{N} regimes. We adopt this simplification not only because deriving spectra of graph families analytically is very hard, but also predicting quantum advantage using classical resources is at least as challenging. Consequently, our extensive numerical analyses are to only be viewed as providing a reasonable understanding of the potential advantage that a graph family offers, and further future work is required in this direction.
- **The classical benchmark algorithm:** The runtime complexity for the fictitious CLS that we choose is set to be the same as that of the well-known conjugate gradient method purely due to favourable scaling in \mathcal{N} , κ , s , and ϵ^{-1} , but the CLS itself should not be thought of as possessing the limitations of the conjugate gradient method such as being restricted only for positive definite matrices. In this context, we acknowledge that other important works exist in literature and by choosing a fictitious CLS as a representative benchmark classical solver to compare QLSs against, we do not do justice to the vast body of literature on classical algorithms for linear systems of equations. We defer a comparison of QLSs against leading classical linear solvers to a future study. Having said this, we pick two realistic specialized classical linear solvers for Laplacians as representative examples to qualitatively comment on our solver as a reasonable candidate. To this end, we pick a graph family from our candidate graph families and carry out a comparison:

 1. The authors in Ref.[9] discuss an efficient method for solving systems of linear equations arising from a graph Laplacian ($(N \times N)$, symmetric, and diagonally dominant matrix), whose associated graph has N vertices and M edges, and which scales as $\tilde{O}(M \log^2(N) \log(1/\epsilon))$. Our goal is to compare this solver, which we shall term the KMP solver (based on the authors’ initials), against our CLS, and we do so by analyzing a situation where the former excels, thereby stacking the odds against CLS. We set $\epsilon^{-1} = \log(N)$. Noting that a graph that has no isolated vertices needs to have at least $N - 1$ edges (best case scenario; the worst case would be $\sim N^2$ edges) and also simplifying $\tilde{O}(f(n)) =$

$O(f(n)\log^k n)$ by setting $k = 1$ (best case scenario), the expression for complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N\log^2(N)\log(1/\epsilon) \log(N\log^2(N)\log(1/\epsilon)))$. For illustration, we now consider the specific case of a graph for which κ and s grow as $\log(N)$. We see that the runtime complexity ratio, $R(N) = t_{\text{CLS}}/t_{\text{HHL}}$, simplifies to $N\log(\log(N))/\log^{5.5}(N)$, which is an exponential advantage. Instead, if we use the KMP algorithm in place of CLS, the runtime ratio is $\frac{(N\log(\log(N))\log[N\log^2(N)\log(\log(N))])}{\log^5(N)}$. Fig. S.2(c) presents the curves for $R(N)$ versus N for the cases of CLS and the KMP solver. We see that using either our CLS or the KMP solver still yields an exponential advantage with HHL.

2. We consider another example, where the authors propose algorithms for solving systems of linear equations that arise in the specific case of graph Laplacians of planar graphs [10, 11]. Their algorithms scale as $\mathcal{O}(M\log(1/\epsilon))$. Assuming $M \sim N$, $1/\epsilon \sim \log(N)$, we obtain $R(N)$ to be $(N\log(\log(N))/\log^7(N))$, which gives an exponential advantage, just as in the case of CLS being used in place of these approaches. Furthermore, these algorithms too reach the crossover point at smaller system sizes.

Thus, we see that qualitatively, the CLS we consider is a reasonable representative example at least for the purposes of our preliminary study to all of the classical linear solvers. For completeness, we comment on a special case of LSP applied to effective resistance determination where the conjugate gradient method works. Since the input vector, \vec{b} has in it one 1, one -1 , and the rest of its elements are 0, the vector is orthogonal to the all-1 vector that lies in the null space of L , and thus conjugate gradient suffices in spite of its limitation in being able to handle only positive definite matrices (for example, see Section 3.2 of Ref. [11]). In fact, this holds when the condition $\sum_i b_i = 0$ is satisfied.

- **Padding the A matrix:** We note that if the A matrix from a problem/application is not of dimension $2^{n_b} \times 2^{n_b}$, we pad the matrix by adding a scalar along the diagonals, that is, $\begin{pmatrix} A_{\text{problem}} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathcal{D} \end{pmatrix}$, where \mathcal{D} is an appropriately chosen diagonal matrix with all the diagonal entries being the same (a scalar matrix), such that we then solve by using a QLS for

the equation $\begin{pmatrix} A_{\text{problem}} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathcal{D} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \vec{x} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{b} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$. We note that the sparsity of the non-padded and the padded matrices remain the same. Furthermore, one needs to ensure that κ remains unaffected with a suitable choice for the scalar in the scalar matrix. We assume that there exists an oracle that supplies an appropriate scalar in such situations. Therefore, for our numerical analyses, we only compute s and κ of the graph Laplacian or graph incidence matrices we consider, and not those of the padded matrices.

- **Function fitting considerations:** When we seek fitting functions for our data points for κ and s of some considered graph, we mainly check the goodness of fit by simple visual inspection as well as tests that check if the fitted functional form gives absurd values for the quantities (for instance, $\kappa < 1$ and $s < 0$). For a not-so-obvious distribution of data points in a graph family, we fit the upper envelope as a reasonable approximation to the quantity in question. We also note that for the case of s , since it is constrained to be a positive integer, we round off the fit sparsity values to their nearest integer value. Furthermore, we only consider for fitting the following candidate functions: exponential, polylogarithmic (at most third order), and polynomial (at most third order). We exclude functions like $1/N^p$; $p \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, since they can lead to ill-behaved situations. For example, the complexity of the phase randomisation algorithm contains in it a $\log(\kappa)$ factor, and in the event that $\kappa \sim 1/N$, the complexity expression is not defined anymore. We also add that wherever analytical expressions are available, we fit that quantity (for example, s) to that expected function. For other cases, which constitute most of our candidates, we restrict ourselves to exponential/ polylogarithmic/ polynomial for simplicity. A caveat is that in spite of all these considerations for the fit function, it may or may not exactly reproduce the actual κ or s behaviour. For instance, we found that for the directed hypercube graph, we could get equally convincing fits within both $\log^2(N')$ and $\log^3(N')$. Although we expect the fit to do a reasonable job in general and not change the graph family category, this will remain an important fundamental limitation in such analyses.

S.5. DETAILS OF THE GRAPH FAMILIES SURVEYED: CONSTRUCTION AND INPUT PARAMETERS

In this section, we list all the classes of graph families which we consider for our numerical investigations. We recall that we consider both random and non-random graphs for our study. A random graph is a graph where the existence of an edge is probabilistic. The probability depends on a seed value. For different seed values, we get different probability functions that result in different graphs belonging to the same class. In a non-random graph, the existence of an edge is deterministic. It is unrealistic to consider all the graphs of the same class of random graphs for a numerical investigation. But fixing the seed value makes a random graph unique, which we consider as a representative of the family of random graphs. Other than the seed values, there can be other parameters that influence the structural properties of the graphs. Therefore, for each of the graphs, we present the seed values and parameters that we set for the numerical calculations in this work. We follow NetworkX (version 3.4.2) for the construction of all random and non-random graphs except the hypercube graphs. In the following two sections, we describe the graphs used for our studies on the system of linear equations generated by the Laplacian matrices and the incidence matrices.

A Graphs whose Laplacian matrices are considered in our study

All the graphs that we utilize in our work are undirected and simple. Our constructions ensure that no self-loop or multiple edges are generated in the graph.

1. Non-Random graphs

1. **Hypercube graphs:** The hypercube graphs are generalizations of cubes in graph theory. The n -dimensional hypercube graph G_2^n has vertex set $V(G_2^n) = \{0, 1\}^{\times n}$ which contains $N = 2^n$ vertices. The Hamming distance $\mathfrak{H}(x, y)$ between two tuples $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ and $y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) \in \{0, 1\}^{\times n}$ is the number of indices i for which $x_i \neq y_i$. There is an edge between vertices x and y if the Hamming distance, $\mathfrak{H}(x, y) = 1$. Note that x_i and y_i are either 0 or 1 for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The dimension n is the only parameter for this class of graphs. In this article, we consider all the hypercube graphs with number of vertices N ranging from 4 to 16384. The illustrations of the hypercube graph can be found in Figure 2(a) of the main manuscript.

2. **Margulis-Gabber-Galil graphs:** In this article, we consider the vertex sets of the Margulis-Gabber-Galil graphs as $\mathbb{Z}_n \times \mathbb{Z}_n$, where $\mathbb{Z}_n = \{\overline{0}, \overline{1}, \overline{2}, \dots, \overline{(n-1)}\}$, \overline{k} is the set of all integers k modulo n , and n is a natural number. Each vertex $(x, y) \in \mathbb{Z}_n \times \mathbb{Z}_n$ is connected to $(x \oplus 2y, y)$, $(x \oplus 2y \oplus 1, y)$, $(x, y \oplus 2x)$ and $(x, y \oplus 2x \oplus 1)$, where \oplus denotes the addition modulo n . This construction would lead to self loops and parallel edges. We modify the graph to exclude self loops and parallel edges from this family. We note that the number of vertices in this family grows as $N = n^2$. We consider all such possible modified Margulis-Gabber-Galil graphs with $25 \leq N \leq 11881$. We depict modified Margulis-Gabber-Galil graphs for $n = 3$ and $n = 6$ in Figure 2(c) of the main manuscript.
3. **Sudoku graphs** [12]: The Sudoku graphs are graphs that consist of $N = n^4$ vertices, which are distributed into the cells of an $n^2 \times n^2$ grid. Every cell contains n^2 vertices. Two distinct vertices are adjacent if they belong to the same row, column, or cell. Thus, every vertex of Sudoku graph is connected to $3n^2 - 2n - 1$ vertices. The quantity d_{max} grows as n^2 , which is also reflected in sparsity of the Laplacian matrix. In our computations, we consider all the Sudoku graphs whose vertices lie in the range of $16 \leq N \leq 104976$. We draw Sudoku graphs in Fig. S.8(a) for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$.
4. **Grid 2d graphs:** To construct a grid 2d graph, we arrange the $N = (r + 1)(c + 1)$ vertices into $(r + 1)$ rows and $(c + 1)$ columns, where $r, c \in \mathbb{N}$. Two distinct vertices are adjacent if they are consecutive in a row or a column. These graphs have two parameters r and c . In our work we consider two families of grid 2d graphs, which are as follows:
 - (a) We fix $r = 101$ and vary c from 5 to 197 to generate a family of graphs whose vertices lie in the range $602 \leq N \leq 20196$. Two grid 2d graphs belonging to this family are depicted in Figure 3(a) of the main manuscript.
 - (b) For the other family of graphs we consider $r + 1 = c + 1 = 2^n$. With this constraint on the number of vertices, we generate graphs with $16 \leq N \leq 65536$. Grid 2d graphs belonging to this family for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ are depicted in Fig. S.9(ak).

Since every vertex is connected to its immediate neighbouring vertices in rows or columns, its degree is at most 4. Therefore, the sparsity of the Laplacian matrix of all the grid 2d graphs is 5.

5. **Hexagonal lattice graphs:** The graph is constructed on a two dimensional plane having r rows and c columns of hexagons. The vertices of the hexagons constitute the vertices of the graph and the edges of the graph are the sides of the hexagons (see Figure 3(c) of the main manuscript). For our analysis, we set $c = 101$ and generate the family of graphs with $r = 1$ to $r = 108$. Thus, the number of vertices lie in the range $406 \leq N \leq 22234$.
6. **Triangular lattice graphs:** The construction involves arranging triangles in r rows and c columns on a two-dimensional plane. The corners of the triangles are the vertices of the graph. Also, the sides of the triangles are the edges of the graph. The number of rows r is varied from 1 to 100 while keeping the number of columns c fixed at 101. The graphs are generated for N in the range $103 \leq N \leq 5202$. Two instances of triangular lattice graphs are presented in Fig. S.9(a).
7. **Complete graphs:** A complete graph is a graph, such that an edge between any two distinct vertices exists. The degree of all the vertices is $N - 1$ in a complete graph with N vertices. We consider all the complete graphs with number of vertices $2 \leq N \leq 5004$. Two instances of this graph can be found in Fig. S.9(c).
8. **Turan graphs:** In general, Turan graphs are constructed from p partitions or disjoint sets of different sizes. For our calculations, we set $p = 2$, making it a bipartite graph. The number of vertices in those two partitions are $\lfloor \frac{N}{2} \rfloor$ and $N - \lfloor \frac{N}{2} \rfloor$. We analyze graphs whose vertices are in the range $5 \leq N \leq 5003$. Two illustrations of the graph family can be found in Fig. S.9(e).
9. $H_{k,n}$ **Harary graphs** [13]: For this family of graphs, we set the vertex connectivity, which refers to the minimum number of edges to be removed from the graph to make it a disconnected graph, to 3. The number of vertices $N = n$ is varied from 5 to 5009. The construction procedure tries to minimize the number of edges in the graph. Two instances of the graph family are presented in Fig. S.9(u).
10. $H_{m,n}$ **Harary graphs** [13] : Given m edges and $N = n$ vertices, this construction yields a graph that ensures maximum vertex connectivity. The number of edges in this family of graphs is set to be one greater than the number of vertices that the graph contains. Here, we generate graphs for $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. We present two graphs from this family in Fig. S.9(w).
11. **Ladder graphs:** A path graph $P = (V, E)$ of order n is a graph with vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E = \{(v_i, v_{i+1}) : \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, (n - 1)\}$. A ladder graph with $N = 2n$ vertices is constructed with all the vertices and edges of two path graphs P_1 and P_2 each of order n as well as the edges $\{(u_i, v_i) : \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } u_i \in V(P_1), v_i \in V(P_2)\}$. We consider all the ladder graphs with $10 \leq N \leq 5000$. Two graphs of this family are presented in Fig. S.9(aa).
12. **Circular ladder graphs:** A cycle graph $C = (V, E)$ of order n is a graph with vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E = \{(v_i, v_{i+1}) : \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, (n - 1)\} \cup \{(v_n, v_1)\}$. A circular ladder graph with $N = 2n$ vertices is constructed with all the vertices and edges of two cycle graphs C_1 and C_2 each of order n as well as the edges $\{(u_i, v_i) : \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } u_i \in V(P_1), v_i \in V(P_2)\}$. In this case also, we consider all the circular ladder graphs with $10 \leq N \leq 5000$. Two graphs of this family are given in Fig. S.9(y).
13. **Ring of cliques:** A clique is a complete subgraph of a graph. A ring of clique is constructed by connecting each clique by a single edge. In this work, we set the number of vertices in each clique to be 3, and thus all cliques are of equal size. Hence, the number of vertices in the graph grows as $N = 3n$, for n cliques. We consider all possible graphs with vertices in the range $15 \leq N \leq 5001$. Fig. S.9(ac).
14. **Balanced trees:** A tree is a graph without any cyclic subgraph. A rooted tree is a tree with a marked vertex called root. Usually, we label it with 0. A leaf is a vertex in a tree with degree 1. We say a tree is a balanced tree if the distance from the root to all the leaf vertices are equal. We call it the height of the balanced tree, which may be considered as a parameter to construct the families of the balanced trees. We denote it by n . If the degree of the root vertex is r then the degree of all other non-leaf vertices is $(r+1)$. We consider the following two families of balanced trees for our investigations:
 - (a) **Balanced binary tree:** In a balanced binary tree the degree of the root vertex $r = 2$. If the height of the tree is n , then the number of vertices, $N = 2^{n+1} - 1$. For our calculations, we consider n from 2 to 14. Two graphs from the graph family are presented in Fig. S.9(ae).

(b) **Balanced ternary tree:** Similarly, in a balanced ternary tree the degree of root vertex $r = 3$. If the height of the tree is n , then the number of vertices, $N = (3^{n+1} - 1)/2$. For our calculations, we consider n from 2 to 9. Two instances are presented in Fig. S.9(ag).

15. **Binomial tree:** A binomial tree of order n is created by linking the root vertices of two identical copies of binomial trees of order $n - 1$. A binomial tree of order 0 has a single vertex and this vertex acts as a root vertex in successive graphs. Suppose that the root vertex of binomial tree of order $n - 1$ is v_1 . We create its identical copy, whose root vertex is now marked as v_c , and join v_1 and v_c to construct a binomial tree of order n . The root vertex v_c can be viewed as the leftmost child of v_1 . The number of vertices, N , in the tree grows as $N = 2^n$. For our calculations, we consider n from 2 to 14. Two instances of the graph family are given in Fig. S.9(ai).

2. Random graphs

For all the below random graphs, we fix the seed value to be 23, unless specified.

1. **Random regular expander graphs:** Our procedure for constructing the random regular expander graph is as follows. We generate a random regular graph with regularity k and N vertices using the construction prescribed in Ref. [14]. Next, we check if the second largest eigenvalue of the adjacency matrix $\lambda_2 \leq 2\sqrt{k - 1}$, where k is an even number. In our construction, we set $k = 6$. Recall that all the Ramanujan graphs [15], which is a prominent family of expander graphs, must fulfill this property. We repeat the procedure at most 200 times for getting a Ramanujan graph. We experience that this process could not produce a Ramanujan graph in 3 percent of the considered values of N , which is a negligible percentage. Varying the value of N between 9 and 5009 we construct a family of Ramanujan graphs, used in our investigation. We present two graphs of this family in Fig. S.8(g).

2. **Barabási-Albert graphs**[16]: The Barabási-Albert graph is a class of random scale-free networks, which grows in size via the following mechanism. A new vertex is adjacent to k old vertices such that the probability of choosing an old vertex depends on the degree of the old vertex. Therefore,

the vertices with high degree are preferred while growing the graph, leading to fewer vertices with large vertex degree. In our analysis, we set $k = 3$ and consider all graphs in this class with the number of vertices $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. Two of the graphs from this family are presented in Fig. S.8(e).

3. **Newman-Watts-Strogatz graphs** [17]: We first arrange N vertices over a ring lattice. Each vertex in the ring is connected to its g nearest neighbors or $(g - 1)$ nearest neighbors if g is odd. Further we add new edges as follows. For each edge (v_i, v_j) in the underlying " N -ring with g nearest neighbors", with probability p add a new edge (v_i, v_k) with randomly chosen existing node v_k . For our analysis, we set $g = 3$ and $p = 1$ with seed value 19. We generate all Newman-Watts-Strogatz graphs with the number of vertices in the range $5 \leq N \leq 5005$. Fig. S.8(c) contains two instances of this family.

4. **Random regular graphs:** We generate the random regular graphs using the algorithms discussed in [18, 19]. Here, the product of the number of vertices N and the regularity k must be an even number. For our calculations, we fix $k = 4$ and generate all graphs with the number of vertices $5 \leq N \leq 5013$. Two graphs from the family are given in Fig. S.8(i).

5. **$G_{n,p}$ random graphs:** We generate all $G_{n,p}$ random graphs, in other words the Erdős-Rényi random graphs [20], with the number of vertices $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. The only parameter in this construction is n which sets the number of vertices in the graph, i.e., $N = n$. Here, we set the probability of existence of an edge between two randomly selected vertices to be $p = 0.8$. Two graphs of this family are given in Fig. S.9(ao).

6. **Gaussian random partition graphs** [21]: A Gaussian random partition graph is constructed by generating k partitions on the set of vertices N . The size of the partitions are drawn from a normal distribution with a fixed mean and variance. For our work, we consider the Gaussian random partition graphs with $k = 5$ partitions whose size is determined by the Gaussian distribution with mean 5 and variance 1. The probability of establishing the edges between two vertices inside a partition is set to be 0.5 and in between the partitions is fixed to be 0.4. For our investigation, we generate all the Gaussian random partition graphs with vertices $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. Two of the graphs from this family are given in Fig. S.9(g).

7. **Geographical threshold graphs** [22, 23]: To construct a graph from this family, we place all the N vertices on a Cartesian plane, with the distances between the vertices chosen at random. Each vertex is assigned a random weight drawn from an exponential distribution with rate parameter $k = 1$, in our case. Two vertices p and q with weights x_p and x_q are connected if $(x_p + x_q)r^{-2} \geq 10$, where r is the Euclidean distance between two vertices. We generate graphs of this family in the range $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. Two of the graphs from this family are presented in Fig. S.9(i).
8. **Soft random geometric graphs** [24]: To construct the soft random geometric graph, we place N vertices randomly on a Cartesian plane. A probability function determines the connection between two vertices, which takes the Euclidean distance between two vertices as an input. If the Euclidean distance, r , between two vertices is at most 1, then the probability of joining them by an edge is decided by the probability density function e^{-r} . Here, we generate graphs with number of vertices $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. Fig. S.9(k) presents two graphs from this family.
9. **Thresholded random geometric graphs**: To construct this graph family, we place N vertices randomly on the Cartesian plane, and each vertex is assigned a weight that is randomly chosen from an exponential distribution of rate parameter k . We set $k = 1$. Two vertices are connected by an edge if the sum of their weights is greater than or equal to 2 and the Euclidean distance between the vertices is less than or equal to 1. We generate graphs with vertices $5 \leq N \leq 5009$. Fig. S.9(m) displays two instances of this graph family.
10. **Planted partition graphs** [25]: A planted partition graph has $N = l \times n$ vertices distributed into l groups with n vertices in each. Two vertices in the same group are linked with a probability p . Two vertices belonging to two different groups are linked with probability q . For our calculations, we consider $l = 2$, $p = 0.5$ and $q = 0.4$. To generate a graph family, we vary n , such that, the number of vertices N varies from 10 to 5014. Fig. S.9(o) presents two instances from this graph family.
11. **Random geometric graphs** [26]: We place N vertices randomly on a Cartesian plane join two vertices by an edge if their Euclidean distance, r is at most 1. For our calculations, we construct a graph family where the the number of vertices range from 7 to 5008. Fig. S.9(q) contains two instances of this graph family.
12. **Uniform random intersection graphs** [27]: These graphs are generated from random bipartite graphs. First, we construct a bipartite graph with two partite sets containing N and $N - 3$ vertices, respectively. The probability of existence of an edge between the partite sets is set to be 0.6. Then, the bipartite graph is projected onto the partite sets having N vertices. There is an edge between two vertices in the resultant graph, if those two vertices share a common neighbor in the first bipartite graph. We vary the number of vertices N from 5 to 2999, due to computational limitations. Fig. S.9(s) represents two graphs belonging to this family.
13. **Random lobster graphs**: This graph is a tree which generates a caterpillar graph when all the leaf vertices are removed. We vary the number of vertices present in the backbone of the graph to generate a family. An edge between two vertices belonging to the backbone of the graph is drawn with probability 0.6, while the probability of edge creation beyond backbone level is set to be 0.5. We set the seed value to 19. The number of vertices in the graph varies in the range $20 \leq N \leq 5014$. Fig. S.9(am) contains two instances of random lobster graph family.

B Graphs whose incidence matrices are considered in our studies

For our work, we have random and non-random directed graphs. These graphs may have a source or a sink vertex by the virtue of their construction. Therefore, we follow two approaches for random directed graphs. In the first approach, we carry out our analysis by retaining the source and sink vertices of the graph, whereas in the second approach, we minimally modify the edge set to not have any sink or source vertices in the graph. In the latter case, the number of vertices remain the same as the original graph. We recall that, for incidence matrices, system size \mathcal{N} refers to the sum of number of vertices and edges, $\mathcal{N} = N' = N + M$. We also do not allow multiple edges and self-loops.

1. Non-random directed graphs

We consider two non-random directed graph-families in our work. Below, we mention them briefly.

1. **Paley graphs:** For an odd prime number N , the vertex set of the Paley graph is $\mathbb{Z}/N\mathbb{Z}$. A directed edge exists from vertex u to w if $u-w \equiv x^2 \pmod{N}$, where $x^2 \in \mathbb{Z}/N\mathbb{Z}$ and N is the number of vertices. Also, to avoid bi-directed edges, $N \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, so that $-1 \not\equiv x^2 \pmod{N}$. We follow the construction given in [28]. Our system size N' varies from 6 to 9730. Fig. S.10(o) presents two instances of this graph family.
2. **Directed hypercube graphs:** Similar to the undirected hypercube graphs of dimension n , we consider the vertex set $V(G_2^n) = \{0, 1\}^{\times n}$ which contains $N = 2^n$ vertices. There is a directed edge from vertex v_1 to v_2 if the Hamming distance between the vertices is 1 and the Hamming weight of $v_1 < v_2$. Here, Hamming weight of a vertex refers to the number of 1s in the corresponding n -tuple. This arrangement of directed edges indicates that there is only one source and sink in a directed hypercube graph. The number of edges in a hypercube graph grows as $2^{n-1}n$. Hence, the system size in a directed hypercube graph grows as $N' = 2^n(1 + n/2) \sim \mathcal{O}(2^n n)$. The number of vertices in the graph assists the graph-family to grow in terms of 2^n , where $n = 2, 3, \dots$. Our system size varies N' from 8 to 131072. Two instances of this graph family can be found in Figure 4(a) of the main manuscript.

2. Random directed graphs

We consider nine random directed graphs in this article. For the sake of reproducibility, we fix seed value of every random directed graph family to be 19. Further, we followed the constructions from Ref. [28] with slight modifications to avoid bi-directed edges and self-loops in the graphs.

1. **GN graph:** A GN graph grows the network by linking a newly added vertex to one of the existing vertices based on their degree. We define a linear function $f(d) = d$, where d is the degree of the vertex. This function determines the probability of connecting the new vertex to one of the existing vertices. In our work, the value of system size N' goes from 9 to 9997 for GN graphs with source and sink vertices. Also, the system size varies from 11 to 9998 for GN graphs without source and sink vertices. Figures 4(e) and 4(g) of the main manuscript present two instances each for without and with source and sink vertices, respectively.

Algorithm1 To modify source/sink vertices to non-source/non-sink vertices

Input: Directed graph, G , with source and/or sink vertices.
Output: Directed graph without source and sink vertices.

- 1: **for** every vertex $v \in V(G)$ **do**
- 2: **if** in-degree(v) + out-degree(v) = 1 **then**
- 3: **if** in-degree(v) = 1 **then**
- 4: Find the vertex u for which $\overrightarrow{(u, v)} \in E(G)$.
- 5: Add edge $\overrightarrow{(v, y)}$ and $y \notin \{v, u\}$ chosen at random.
- 6: **else**
- 7: Find the vertex u for which $\overrightarrow{(v, u)} \in E(G)$.
- 8: Add edge $\overrightarrow{(y, v)}$ and $y \notin \{v, u\}$ chosen at random.
- 9: **end if**
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **end for**
- 12: Create two lists containing the source and sink vertices: *source*, *sink*.
- 13: **if** *source* and *sink* are empty **then**
- 14: print "There are no source and sink vertices in the graph".
- 15: **else if** *source* is empty **then**
- 16: Create *list1* = $\{u | u \notin \textit{sink}\}$.
- 17: Add edges from vertices in *sink* to vertices in *list1* chosen at random. If there are edges toward *sink* from vertices in *list1* whose out-degree > 1, reverse them.
- 18: **else if** *sink* is empty **then**
- 19: Create *list2* = $\{v | v \notin \textit{source}\}$.
- 20: Add edges towards vertices in *source* from vertices in *list2* chosen at random. If there are edges from *source* to vertices in *list2* whose in-degree > 1, reverse them.
- 21: **else if** length(*source*) \leq length(*sink*) **then**
- 22: Add an edge from sink vertex to corresponding source vertex without creating a bi-directed edge.
- 23: For the remaining sink vertices, choose vertices from *source* at random and build an edge from sink vertex to a randomly chosen source vertex.
- 24: **else**
- 25: Repeat step 22.
- 26: For the remaining source vertices, add edges from randomly chosen sink vertices to these source vertices.
- 27: **end if**

2. **GNC graph** [29]: A GNC graph is grown by adding a directed edge from a new vertex to an existing vertex chosen randomly. Further, directed edges go from the new vertex to the successors of the existing vertex to which it is connected. A vertex, v_u , is said to be the successor to a vertex v_w , if there is a directed edge going from v_w to v_u . For GNC graphs with source and sink vertices, we con-

sider N' in the range of 11 to 8498. Also, for the family of GNC graphs without any source and sink vertices, the system size N' varies from 11 to 6759. Two GNC graphs without and with source and sink vertices are depicted in Figs. S.11(a) and S.11(c) respectively.

3. **GNR graph** [30]: The construction of the GNR graphs is similar to the GN graphs. Here, when a new vertex is added, a directed edge appears from the new vertex to a randomly chosen existing vertex, called the target vertex. There is a finite chance for this new directed edge to get redirected to first successor of target vertex. For our work, we set the probability of reconnection to 0.5. For the GNR graphs with source and sink vertices, the system size grows from 9 to 9997. Also, for GNR graphs without source and sink vertices, N' varies from 12 to 10000. Figs. S.11(e) and S.11(g) respectively present the figures for graphs without and with source and sink vertices belonging to this family.
4. **Gaussian random partition graphs:** The underlying principles for the directed Gaussian random partition graph is similar to its undirected version as described in sub-section S.5 A 2. We follow the construction from Ref. [28] to build directed Gaussian random partition graphs. The values of the parameters to build this graph family are same as the values set in the undirected version. We vary N' from 12 to 10897 for both the cases. Figure 4(c) contains two instances of this family for without source and sink vertices and Figure S.10(a) has illustrations of two graphs for with source and sink vertices of this family.
5. **Planted partition graphs:** Our construction for the planted partition graph is also similar to their undirected mentioned in the sub-section S.5 A 2. Here, we fix the number of vertices present in each partition to be 5 and vary the number of partitions to grow the graph. We set the probability of linking vertices inside a partition to 0.8 and between the partitions to 0.4. For graphs with sink and source vertices, we vary N' from 228 to 24405. For graphs without sink and source vertices, we vary N' from 228 to 20208. Two graphs each for without and with source and sink vertices are presented in Figs. S.10(c) and S.10(e) respectively.
6. **Navigable small world graphs** [31]: The graph is defined on a two-dimensional $n \times n$ grid with $N = n^2$ vertices. The distance between two vertices (a, b)

and (c, d) is defined as $\mathcal{R} = |a - c| + |b - d|$. Based on the distance between vertices, we define short-range and long-range connections. A vertex (a, b) is connected to all vertices which are at distance 1 to it. The number of long-range connections of a vertex is set to 1. The probability of connecting the vertex to a target vertex at a distance \mathcal{R} is proportional to $1/\mathcal{R}^2$. For graphs without source and sink vertices, N' is varied from 84 to 20537, whereas for graphs with source and sink vertices, N' goes from 83 to 14827. Figs. S.10(g) and S.10(i) show two graphs each for without and with source and sink vertices corresponding to this family.

7. **$G_{n,p}$ random graphs:** Our construction for the $G_{n,p}$ random graph is also similar to their counterparts mentioned in the sub-section S.5 A 2 with same values for the parameters. For graphs without sink and source vertices, N' is varied from 44 to 42534, while for graphs with sink and source vertices, N' ranges from 44 to 21721. Two graphs each for without and with source and sink vertices can be found in Figs. S.10(k) and S.10(m) respectively.
8. **Random uniform k -out graphs:** In this graph, k directed edges go from every vertex of the graph to k vertices chosen randomly without replacement. For our calculations, we set $k = 2$. For graphs with source and sink, N' takes the values from 12 to 10943 and graphs without source and sink, N' goes from 13 to 10817. Figs. S.10(q) and S.10(s) present two graphs each for without and with source and sink vertices respectively.
9. **Scale-free graphs** [32]: In this graph family, the in-degree and out-degree distributions of vertices follow power laws. We start with a cycle graph with 3 edges. A directed edge from a new vertex to an existing vertex, chosen according to its in-degree distribution, is added with probability 0.41. An edge between two existing vertices are added with probability 0.54 and the vertices are chosen according to their in-degree and out-degree distributions. The probability of adding a directed edge from an existing vertex, chosen according to its out-degree distribution, to a new vertex is 0.05. The probability of choosing an existing vertex would depend on the in-degree (or out-degree) in addition to a constant bias. The constant bias for in-degree distribution is set to be $\delta_{\text{in}} = 0.2$ and for out-degree distribution is set to be $\delta_{\text{out}} = 0$. Here, we vary the system size N from 12 to 10997 for graphs without sink and source vertices. For graphs with sink and source vertices,

\mathcal{N} is varied from 11 to 9995. Figs. S.10(u) and S.10(w) present two instances each for graph without and with source and sink vertices respectively.

S.6. BEYOND GRAPH THEORETIC CONSIDERATIONS: OTHER REQUIREMENTS AND CHALLENGES

A Algorithmic challenges

1. **State preparation for $|b\rangle$:** This scales exponentially in system size in a general setting, and is one of those important open problems not only for QLSs, but also whenever one employs quantum phase estimation (QPE) as a primitive, and is a major impediment to quantum advantage even if other factors align in our favour. Depending on the specific application of interest, one may be able to identify problem-specific symmetries to reduce the scaling.
2. **Extracting a feature of the solution vector:** HHL, for example, loses its exponential advantage if we seek to extract the solution vector, \vec{x} . Therefore, in practice, one needs to extract a feature of the vector and not the vector itself. For instance, if one considers the traffic flow problem in Fig. 1 of the main manuscript, and asks what a particular x_i is, that is, the number of vehicles on that particular lane, then one could append a SWAP test module at the end of the HHL circuitry in order to obtain an overlap between the solution vector and a computational basis vector to obtain x_i . This is reasonable for a traffic flow congestion detection problem, as often, one would want to only understand the traffic congestion on specific lanes and not all the exponentially many lanes in a network. However, the ability to extract a feature is application-dependent, and it is unclear whether or not an efficient protocol exists for feature extraction for any application.
3. NLSPs often occur in the context of optimization problems, where one envisages an **iterative procedure** that involves, for example, executing several HHLs in tandem. Such an execution is hardly straightforward, especially given the post-selection step at the end of each iteration.
4. **Constraints imposed by specific applications:** If we consider the traffic flow congestion detection

problem, the elements of the solution vector are constrained to be positive integers. Furthermore, the application can also naturally admit overdetermined or underdetermined systems, and interpreting the solutions themselves is no longer straightforward. In such cases, modifications to the quantum algorithm and/or the preceding classical or quantum pre-processing steps and their net effect on advantage offered is unclear.

B Quantum hardware challenges

1. **NISQ era requirements:** Although HHL and other QLSs discussed in this work are outside of the scope of NISQ computers and would ideally require a fault-tolerant implementation, it is important to test these solvers on smaller system sizes for various applications even in the NISQ era, continuously pushing the boundaries as quantum hardware advances. A typical theme in carrying out such computations would be to rely upon classical resources (which do not necessarily scale well) to reduce quantum circuit depth and number of qubits, we term these gamut of techniques as resource reduction. In Section VII.1 of the main manuscript, we illustrated these ideas through toy graph instances. Our results show that with current quantum hardware capabilities, we can only probe (4×4) size Laplacian matrices (unless we find special graphs and leverage techniques like all-qubit fixing, as explained in Section VII.2 of the main manuscript), indicating the actual gap between what is possible and what is our goal for the long-term. For perspective, it is routine to solve systems of linear equations involving matrices that are about $(10^9 \times 10^9)$ in size, for example, in quantum chemical computations on traditional computers [33].
2. **Fault-tolerant quantum computing era requirements:** Of most relevance in the late NISQ/early fault-tolerant quantum computing eras would be graph families that provide exponential speed-up and polynomial speed-up (with a larger-than-quadratic degree polynomial), in view of overheads associated with quantum error corrected implementations eating up a sub-linear or a lower degree polynomial speed-up offered by good graph families and some better graph families (for example, see Ref. [34], where the authors show that quadratic speedups will not enable quantum advantage on early generation fault-tolerant computers that use surface codes). It is hard to predict the extent to

which such issues will plague good and better graph families in the fault-tolerant quantum computing era, where one can use codes with lower thresholds. However, in all of these cases, one aims at reducing either the runtime or the number of physical qubits or in an ideal case, both of them, in fault-tolerant QLS implementations. This would in turn depend on achieving lower physical error rates and faster gate times in the quantum hardware that is used, as well as choice of suitable quantum error correction codes. Each of these is formidable, and until these obstacles are cleared, truly realizing an advantage even with better and best graphs is hard.

S.7. SOME THEOREMS RELEVANT TO ALL-QUBIT FIXING

Theorem S.7.1. *Given a Laplacian matrix, L , and a vector, \vec{b} , such that it has for its entries exactly one 1 and one -1 with the rest of its entries being 0, any problem to be solved using the HHL algorithm reduces to a one-qubit calculation via all-qubit fixing as long as the input \vec{b} is an eigenvector of L .*

Proof. If \vec{b} is an eigenvector of L , a QPE calculation would yield only the eigenvalue corresponding to \vec{b} , that is, only one bitstring. Thus, all the qubits get fixed in the subsequent HHL calculation. Therefore, every clock register qubit of the QPE module of HHL is set to either $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$, and hence the state register has correspondingly either identity ($I_{2^{n_b} \times 2^{n_b}}$) or a unitary ($U^{2^{n_r}} = e^{iAt2^{n_r}}$) respectively. Each gate cancels out with its counterpart in the following QPE † module. Thus, we get back $|b\rangle$ at the end of the circuit, that is, $|\langle x|b\rangle| = 1$. The controlled-rotation module that occurs between QPE and QPE † only now has $RY(\theta_i)$ gates on the HHL ancillary qubit register. In fact, since we recover the eigenvalue corresponding to the input eigenstate, only one θ_i is non-zero. We measure Z on this trivial one-qubit computation to obtain $P(1) = |||x\rangle_{un}||^2$. \square

Theorem S.7.2. *The conditions on L so that $\vec{b} = \vec{\delta}_i - \vec{\delta}_j$ is an eigenvector of the matrix are given by $l_{pi} = l_{pj}, \forall p \notin \{i, j\}$, and $l_{ii} = l_{jj}$.*

Proof. Let $L\vec{b} = \beta\vec{b}$. Since, $\vec{b} = \vec{\delta}_i - \vec{\delta}_j$, we have $b_i = 1$ and $b_j = -1$. The action of L , whose matrix elements are

denoted by l_{pq} , on the vector \vec{b} is given by

$$L \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \dots \\ 0 \\ b_i \\ 0 \\ \dots \\ 0 \\ b_j \\ 0 \\ \dots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} l_{1i} - l_{1j} \\ l_{2i} - l_{2j} \\ \dots \\ l_{i-1 i} - l_{i-1 j} \\ l_{ii} - l_{ij} \\ l_{i+1 i} - l_{i+1 j} \\ \dots \\ l_{j-1 i} - l_{j-1 j} \\ l_{ji} - l_{jj} \\ l_{j+1 i} - l_{j+1 j} \\ \dots \\ l_{Ni} - l_{Nj} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{S.13})$$

Noting that the right hand side should equal $\beta\vec{b}$, we arrive at the conditions

$$\boxed{l_{pi} = l_{pj}, \forall p \neq i, j, \text{ and } l_{ii} = l_{jj}.} \quad (\text{S.14})$$

\square

Theorem S.7.2 indicates that the degree of vertices i and j must be equal. Also, for any vertex p in the graph, either both i and j are adjacent to p or not adjacent to p . Therefore, both i and j have same sets of neighbors. Also, if there is no edge between i and j , the distance between them is 2. Given any graph, G , we can construct a new graph, H , by adding two new vertices and a set of edges, such that H will satisfy the conditions of Theorem S.7.2.

Theorem S.7.3. *Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be any graph with the set of vertices $V(G) = \{v_i : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}$ and set of edges $E(G)$. Let $H = (V(H), E(H))$ be a graph such that $V(H) = V(G) \cup \{v_{(N+1)}, v_{(N+2)}\}$ and set of edges $E(H) = E(G) \cup \{(v_{(N+1)}, u_1), (v_{(N+1)}, u_2), \dots, (v_{(N+1)}, u_k)\} \cup \{(v_{(N+2)}, u_1), (v_{(N+2)}, u_2), \dots, (v_{(N+2)}, u_k)\}$, where $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k \in V(G)$ in some order. Then, the Laplacian matrix $L(H)$ has eigenvalue k with an eigenvector $\vec{b} = \underbrace{(0, 0, \dots, 0)}_{N \text{ times}}, 1, -1)^T$.*

Proof. We know that $L(H) = D(H) - Q(H)$, where $D(H)$ and $Q(H)$ are the degree matrix and the adjacency matrix of the graph H , respectively. Denote $L(H) = (l_{ij})_{(N+2) \times (N+2)}$ where

$$l_{ij} = \begin{cases} d_i^{(H)} & \text{if } i = j; \\ -1 & \text{if } (i, j) \in E(H); \\ 0 & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

where $d_i^{(H)}$ is the degree of vertex v_i in the graph H . Now multiply $L(H)$ with the vector \vec{b} . The i -th row of $L(H) \times \vec{b}$ is

$$(L(H)\vec{b})_{i\bullet} = \sum_{j=1}^{N+2} l_{ij}b_j, \quad (\text{S.15})$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, (N+2)$. Let $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_N = 0$. Now, consider the following cases:

Case 1: Let v_i be a vertex other than $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k, v_{(N+1)}$, and $v_{(N+2)}$. Now, $l_{i(N+1)} = l_{i(N+2)} = 0$. Also, $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_N = 0$. Therefore, $(L(H)\vec{b})_{i\bullet} = 0$.

Case 2: Let u_q be any one of u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k . Note that the rows of $L(H)$ corresponding to u_q always have two non-zero entries $l_{q(N+1)} = l_{q(N+2)} = -1$. As $b_1 = b_2 = \dots = b_N = 0$, we have $\sum_{j=1}^N l_{qj}b_j = 0$. As $b_{(N+1)}$ and $b_{(N+2)}$ have opposite signs, we have $l_{q(N+1)}b_{(N+1)} + l_{q(N+2)}b_{(N+2)} = 0$.

Case 3: Let $i = (N+1)$ or $i = (N+2)$. Note that the degrees of $(N+1)$ and $(N+2)$ are $d_{(N+1)}^{(H)} = d_{(N+2)}^{(H)} = k$. Therefore $l_{(N+1)(N+1)} = l_{(N+2)(N+2)} = k$. Now, $(L(H)b)_{(N+1)\bullet} = k$ and $(L(H)b)_{(N+2)\bullet} = -k$.

Combining all the cases, we observe that

$$L(H)\vec{b} = (\underbrace{0, 0, \dots, 0}_{n \text{ times}}, k, -k)^\top = k\vec{b}. \quad (\text{S.16})$$

Therefore, $L(H)$ has an eigenvalue k with eigenvector \vec{b} . \square

Theorem S.7.4. *A complete graph accommodates a one-qubit HHL via all-qubit fixing.*

Proof. The degree matrix, D , is a diagonal matrix with all N entries taking the value $(N-1)$, and thus the condition $l_{ii} = l_{jj}$ is satisfied. Furthermore, since a complete graph is all-to-all connected by construction, $l_{ij} = -1, \forall i \neq j$. Thus, the second condition is satisfied too. Therefore, the Laplacian of a complete graph satisfies Theorem S.7.2, and hence Theorem S.7.1.

An important implication for the complete graph is that one need not *find* an eigenvector; the 1 and -1 entries of \vec{b} can be placed anywhere and such a resulting \vec{b} is still an eigenvector. \square

Figure S.3: Figures providing the edge weight analysis of the hypercube graph family for three different edge weight functions: logarithmic, given in sub-figures (a) and (b), where the edge weight function $w_{ij} = \log(j + 5)$, linear, given in sub-figures (c) and (d) with $w_{ij} = j + 1$, and polynomial, shown in sub-figures (e) and (f) for the polynomial function defined by $w_{ij} = j^2 + 1$.

Figure S.4: Figures presenting the analysis for modified Margulis-Gabber-Galil graph family, for which each vertex is denoted by a tuple (p, q) . Plots (a) and (b) contain the analysis for graphs with logarithmic edge weights defined as $w_{(p,q)(r,s)} = \log(nr + s + 1) + 1$, while sub-figures (c) and (d) presents our results for linear edge weights, $w_{(p,q)(r,s)} = nr + s + 1$, and (e) and (f) show the results for edge weight function $w_{(p,q)(r,s)} = (nr + s + 1)^2$. Here, the number of vertices in the graph is $N = n^2$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

(l)

(Continued)

Figure S.5: Figures representing the difference in minimum eigenvalues between two threshold choices, 10^{-6} (our main results) and 10^{-10} , for those considered graph Laplacians whose minimum eigenvalues show a downward trend with system size, N .

(Continued)

Figure S.6: Figures representing the difference in minimum eigenvalues between two threshold choices, 10^{-6} (our main results) and 10^{-10} , for those considered graph incidence matrices whose minimum eigenvalues show a downward trend with system size, N' .

(Continued)

Figure S.7: Subfigures (a)-(f) show the advantage offered by Barabási-Albert graph family for three different seed values: 10, 23 and 50. Subfigures (g)-(l) represent advantages offered by directed Gaussian random partition graph family for seed values 10, 19 and 50. From (m) - (r), figures demonstrate the advantages offered by planted partition graph for seed values: 10, 12 and 50.

(Continued)

Figure S.8: Sub-figures showing κ and s behaviour of good graphs listed in Table II of the main manuscript.

(Continued)

(o)

(p)

(Continued)

(Continued)

(Continued)

(ag)

(ah)

(ai)

(aj)

(ak)

(al)

(am)

(an)

(Continued)

Figure S.9: Sub-figures showing κ and s behaviour of bad graphs listed in Table III of main manuscript. We also plot the runtime ratios for different QLSs, considered in our study, with the numerical data.

(Continued)

(Continued)

Figure S.10: Sub-figures showing κ and s behaviour of different good graphs listed in Table IV of the main manuscripts as well as runtime ratios of different QLSs obtained from our numerical data. Sub-figures of first two graph families from Table IV can be found in the main manuscript.

Figure S.11: Sub-figures showing κ and s behaviour of different bad graphs listed in Table V of the main manuscript and plots of runtime ratios with different QLSs considered in our study.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(Continued)

Figure S.12: We have presented one instance from those graph families whose condition number was polylog function of \mathcal{N} . We observe that for all these graph families, the entries in the adjacency matrix, thus the Laplacian matrix appear diffused throughout the matrix.

Figure S.13: We have presented one instance from those graph families whose condition number was a polynomial function of \mathcal{N} . For all the graph families mentioned here, we witness a sharp structure in their adjacency matrix and so in its Laplacian matrix.

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